

SEARCH FOR NEW AMOEBACIDES. PART IV

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Syntheses of 2- β -diethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-5- or -7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinolines have been effected having alkyl substitution of Me, Et, Prⁿ, Buⁿ and amylⁿ groups with the object of observing their amoebacidal activity.

Some halo-8-hydroxyquinolines, like chinifon, vioform and diodoquine, possess pronounced amoebacidal activity. Burckhalter and Edgerton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4837) observed high *in vitro* amoebacidal activity in 5-chloro-7-diethylaminomethyl-8-quinolinol. Koushiva (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16C, 224) observed high *in vitro* amoebacidal activity existing among compounds of the types A and B, where R = Buⁿ or C₆H₁₁ⁿ. In view of these observations it has been considered worthwhile to synthesise and investigate amoebacidal activity in compounds of the type C. These compounds:

have been synthesised by the following route:

Yields of compounds of type (I) gradually decrease with the increase of carbon atom in the alkyl group. Iodination of compounds (IV) has been attempted with

different iodinating agents, like a solution of I_2 in KI in aqueous, alcoholic and acetic acid media, iodine in benzene as well as ICl in chloroform, benzene and acetic acid media respectively; but in all cases erratic results have been obtained. Iodination has been effected successfully by gradual acidification with dilute acetic acid a mixture of compound (IV) in dilute KOH and iodine in dilute KOH. The exact position of iodine (5 to 7) has not been ascertained. Hydrochloride or hydriodide of compound (C) ($R=C_6H_{13}$) could not be crystallised.

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

2:3-Dimethyl-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R=Me).—A mixture of *o*-anisidine (1 M), 2-methyl acetoacetic ester (1 M) and a few drops of HCl (dil.) was kept overnight and it was then heated in an oil-bath at 120° to 130° in a Dean and Stark apparatus till no more water had collected. Benzene was then distilled off on the oil-bath and the residual viscous mass was poured into boiling diphenyl oxide. After boiling for 15 minutes, the mass was cooled, diluted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$), kept overnight, filtered and washed with fresh petroleum ether. The crude yield was 55%. It crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. $289-91^\circ$. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 6.6. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 70.94; H, 6.4%).

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R=Et) was prepared from a mixture of *o*-anisidine and 2-ethyl acetoacetic ester in 65% yield. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 288° . (Found: C, 71.5; H, 6.7. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 71.88; H, 6.91%).

2-Methyl-3-propylⁿ-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R=Prⁿ) was prepared from a mixture of *o*-anisidine and 2-propylⁿ acetoacetic ester in 57% yield. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. $198-200^\circ$. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 7.1. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 72.73; H, 7.36%).

2-Methyl-3-butylⁿ-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R=Buⁿ) was prepared from a mixture of *o*-anisidine and 2-butylⁿ acetoacetic ester in 52% yield. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. $196-97^\circ$. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 7.5. $C_{15}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 73.47; H, 7.75%).

2-Methyl-3-amylⁿ-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R=amylⁿ) was prepared from a mixture of *o*-anisidine and 2-amylⁿ acetoacetic ester in 55% yield. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 165° . (Found: C, 73.9; H, 7.9. $C_{16}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 74.13; H, 8.12%).

2-Methyl-3-hexylⁿ-4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline (I:R= C_6H_{13} ⁿ) was prepared from a mixture of *o*-anisidine and 2-hexylⁿ acetoacetic ester in 42% yield. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 152° . (Found: C, 74.4; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2N$ requires C, 74.71; H, 8.42%).

2:3-Dimethyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II:R=Me).—A mixture of (I:R=Me) (15 g.), $POCl_3$ (35 c.c.) and PCl_5 (3 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at $125-30^\circ$ for 5 hours. The product was then cooled and poured on ice. The aqueous solution was partly neutralised, clarified with charcoal and basified with ammonia under cooling. The chloro compound separated out in fine needles. It was crystallised

* Melting point are uncorrected.

from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless fine needles, m.p. 132-33°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{11}ONCl$ requires C, 65.01; H, 5.41%). The picrate crystallised from alcohol in deep yellow needles, m.p. 204-206°.

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II: R = Et) was crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) in colorless fine needles, m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 5.0. $C_{13}H_{14}ONCl$ requires C, 66.24; H, 5.94%). The picrate crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 163-65°.

2-Methyl-3-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II: R = Prⁿ) was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 122-23°. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 6.1. $C_{14}H_{15}ONCl$ requires C, 67.33; H, 6.41%). The picrate was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 165-66°.

2-Methyl-3-butyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II: R = Buⁿ) was crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 6.6. $C_{15}H_{16}ONCl$ requires C, 68.31; H, 6.83%). The picrate was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 165-67°.

2-Methyl-3-amyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II: R = amylⁿ) was crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 101-102°. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 7.0. $C_{16}H_{18}ONCl$ requires C, 69.18; H, 7.2%). The picrate was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 161-62°.

2-Methyl-3-hexyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (II: R = C₆H₁₃ⁿ) was similarly crystallised in colorless needles, m.p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 7.2. $C_{17}H_{20}ONCl$ requires C, 69.98; H, 7.55%). The picrate was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 130-32°.

2-β-Diethylaminoethyl-3-methyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (III: R = Me).—A mixture of (II: R = Me) (6.6 g.), diethylamine hydrochloride (3.3 g.), paraformaldehyde (1.8 g.) and 3 drops of HCl (conc.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath. After an hour a further amount of paraformaldehyde (1 g.) was added and heating continued for another 2 hours. Alcohol was removed on a water-bath, the product was dissolved in water, basified with NaOH and the base was extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was dehydrated (Na₂SO₄) and dry HCl gas was passed in it when the hydrochloride separated out. It was then filtered and washed with dry acetone. The substance was highly hygroscopic. The picrate was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol in brown needles, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{23}H_{26}O_3N_5Cl$ requires N, 13.07%).

The picrates of other 2-β-diethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-8-methoxyquinolines (III: R = alkyl) are described in Table I. These were all crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE I

Picrate of (III). R =	Cryst. shape.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
Et.	Brown needles	178-79°	$C_{24}H_{26}O_3N_5Cl$	13.10	12.74
Pr ⁿ	Yellow "	158-60°	$C_{25}H_{30}O_3N_5Cl$	12.60	12.43
Bu ⁿ	" "	151-52°	$C_{26}H_{34}O_3N_5Cl$	12.30	12.12
Amyl ⁿ	" "	129-30°	$C_{27}H_{38}O_3N_5Cl$	12.10	11.83
Hexyl ⁿ	" "	139-40°	$C_{28}H_{42}O_3N_5Cl$	11.40	11.55

2-β-Diethylaminoethyl-3-methyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline (IV: R = Me).—A mixture of crude (III: R=Me) (7 g.), H₂SO₄ (conc., 50 c.c.) and water (28 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours. The product was then poured on ice, partly neutralised, clarified with charcoal and finally basified with NH₃ under cooling. The viscous brownish mass was then dissolved in dilute NaOH solution. On acidification with acetic acid, a semisolid hydroxy compound separated out. It developed a greenish colour with FeCl₃ in alcoholic solution. The *picrate* was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 193-94°. (Found: N, 13.6. C₂₂H₂₄O₃N₂Cl requires N, 13.43%).

Picrates of 2-β-diethylaminoethyl-3-alkyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinolines (IV) were crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles. The m.p. and analysis of the picrates are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Picrates of (IV). R =	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
Et	190-92°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	13.10	13.07
Pr ⁿ	170-71°	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.80	12.74
Bu ⁿ	115-16°	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.30	12.43
Amyl ⁿ	125-16°	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.50	12.12
Hexyl ⁿ	126-27°	C ₂₇ H ₃₄ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.10	11.82

TABLE III

(C) R =	Halides.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Formula.	%Iodine.	
					Found.	Calc.
Et	HCl	EtOH + EtAc	184-86°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ I	26.60	27.08
Et	HI	EtOH	166-68°			
Pr ⁿ	HI	"	177-79°	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ I ₂	43.80	44.20
Bu ⁿ	HI	"	172-73°	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₂ ClI ₂	43.05	43.70
Amyl ⁿ	HCl	EtAc + EtOH	162-64°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ OO ₂ Cl ₂ I	24.20	24.85

2-β-Diethylaminoethyl-3-methyl-4-chloro-5- or -7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (C: R = Me).—Crude (IV: R=Me) (5 g.) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of 2% KOH and filtered. To this solution was added a solution of iodine (5 g. in 100 c.c. of 3% KOH) and the mixture was gradually acidified with dilute acetic acid under stirring during a period of half an hour. The mass was left overnight, filtered, triturated with a solution of dilute Na₂S₂O₃ and NH₃. The pasty greenish brown mass was then dissolved in benzene, the benzene solution was dried (Na₂SO₄). *Hydrochloride* was prepared by passing dry HCl gas into the benzene solution under cooling. Monohydrochloride crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 185-86°. (Found: I, 27.1. C₁₈H₂₁ON₂Cl₂I requires I, 27.9%).

The properties of hydrochlorides and hydroiodides of other 5- or 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinolines (C) are recorded in Table III.

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